

1 **Impacts of ice-shelf melting on water mass transformation in the Southern**
2 **Ocean from E3SM simulations**

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ABSTRACT

16 The Southern Ocean overturning circulation is driven by both winds and
17 buoyancy from freshwater sources, and among these sources of freshwater,
18 Antarctic sea-ice formation and melting play the dominant role (followed by
19 precipitation). Even though ice-shelf melt is relatively small in magnitude, it
20 is located close to regions of convection, where it may also have an influence
21 on dense water formation. Here, we explore the impacts of ice-shelf melting
22 on Southern Ocean water mass transformation (WMT) using simulations from
23 the Energy Exascale Earth System Model (E3SM) both with and without the
24 explicit representation of melt fluxes from beneath Antarctic ice shelves. We
25 find that ice-shelf melting produces upwelling of Upper Circumpolar Deep
26 Water (UCDW) and this upwelled water is directly converted to lower density
27 values. While the overall differences in Southern Ocean WMT between the
28 two simulations are moderate, freshwater fluxes produced by ice-shelf melting
29 have a further, indirect impact on the Southern Ocean overturning circulation
30 through their interaction with sea-ice formation and melting, which also cause
31 considerable upwelling. We further find that surface freshening and cool-
32 ing by ice-shelf melting causes increased Antarctic sea-ice production and
33 stronger density stratification near the Antarctic coast. The increased stratifi-
34 cation reduces vertical heat transport from the deeper ocean, trapping warmer
35 water at depth. Although the addition of ice-shelf melting processes leads to
36 no significant changes in Southern Ocean WMT, the simulations and analy-
37 sis conducted here imply that increased Antarctic ice-shelf melting in recent
38 decades has likely increased the role of sea ice in Southern Ocean overturning.

39 **1. Introduction**

40 The Southern Ocean plays a large role in Earth's climate system (Merino et al. 2018) as a signif-
41 icant sink for atmospheric heat (Roemmich et al. 2015) and anthropogenic carbon dioxide (Sallée
42 et al. 2012), hence reducing global warming (Merino et al. 2018). The Southern Ocean also pro-
43 duces the densest water mass in the global ocean, Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW), which plays
44 an active role in driving the global meridional overturning circulation (MOC). In turn, the freez-
45 ing and melting of Antarctic sea ice are a major control on this overturning circulation. Using a
46 water mass transformation (WMT) analysis (Walsh 1982), Abernathy et al. (2016) revealed that
47 differential brine rejection and sea-ice melting are strong controls on the strength of the MOC by
48 governing the upwelling and transformation of Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW), with precipita-
49 tion playing a more minor part.

50 Despite a recent sharp, decreasing trend from 2014 to 2019 (Parkinson 2019), most observa-
51 tional studies report increasing Antarctic sea-ice extent during the last 40 years. Most CMIP5
52 models, however, simulate a steadily decreasing Antarctic sea-ice extent over the past few decades
53 (Flato et al. 2013), failing to capture the observed expansion. Significant effort has gone in to
54 understanding the cause for this discrepancy, primarily through the investigation of changes in
55 atmospheric climate modes and their relation to tropical forcing (Thompson et al. 2011; Turner
56 et al. 2009; Stammerjohn et al. 2008; Li et al. 2014; Kwok et al. 2016), ozone depletion (Bitz and
57 Polvani 2012; Sigmond and Fyfe 2010), and ocean and sea-ice feedbacks (Zhang 2007). Increased
58 Antarctic ice-shelf melting could also be contributing to Antarctic sea-ice expansion through the
59 freshening of Southern Ocean surface waters (Jacobs et al. 2002; Jacobs and Giulivi 2010; Merino
60 et al. 2018). Currently, however, ice sheet freshwater fluxes are typically not treated realistically in
61 CMIP5 climate models; freshwater enters the ocean at the ice sheet edge, is distributed near the sea

62 surface, and temporal variability enters only through changes in precipitation. These simplifica-
63 tions may partially explain the failure of existing climate models at mimicking observed Antarctic
64 sea-ice trends (Turner et al. 2013; Zhang et al. 2019).

65 Ice-shelf melt fluxes, though relatively small in magnitude compared to freshwater fluxes from
66 sea-ice freezing and melting or precipitation, may have a disproportionate influence on dense wa-
67 ter formation because they occur at depth, forming a buoyant plume that contributes to ocean
68 overturning. In addition to its direct impacts, ice-shelf melting contributes to freshwater fluxes
69 indirectly through its impacts on stratification and circulation, which feeds back on sea-ice for-
70 mation and melting (Donat-Magnin et al. 2017; Jourdain et al. 2017; Mathiot et al. 2017). While
71 not previously applied to simulations that include thermodynamic interactions with ice shelves,
72 the WMT framework (Walin 1982; Abernathey et al. 2016) is an ideal tool for obtaining a more
73 qualitative and quantitative understanding of how Antarctic ice-shelf melt fluxes impact Southern
74 Ocean properties and circulation.

75 In this study, we investigate the impacts of Antarctic ice-shelf melting on Southern Ocean WMT
76 and its indirect impacts on sea-ice formation and melting. Our approach is that of a sensitiv-
77 ity study, where a perturbed simulation includes an additional source of freshwater derived from
78 explicitly calculating ice-shelf melt fluxes that is not present in the control. This approach also
79 provides an assessment of mechanisms by which increased ice-shelf melting, observed in Antarc-
80 tica during the last few decades (e.g., Shepherd et al. 2004; Khazendar et al. 2016; Pritchard et al.
81 2012; Holland et al. 2019) might impact the broader climate. In Section 2, we briefly describe the
82 E3SM climate model, the reference data sets used for model validation, and the WMT analysis
83 used herein. Section 3 analyzes the fidelity of E3SM’s Southern Ocean climate compared to avail-
84 able reanalysis data sets. Section 4 uses the WMT framework to examine interactions between
85 ice-shelf melting and Southern Ocean sea ice processes and Section 5 provides a detailed analysis

86 of the WMT caused by Antarctic ice-shelf melting. In Section 6, we present our summary and
87 conclusions from this study.

88 **2. Data and Methodology**

89 *a. E3SM*

90 For this study we use the Energy Exascale Earth System Model (E3SM) version 1, a new global,
91 coupled Earth system model developed by the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) (Golaz et al.
92 2019; Petersen et al. 2019; Rasch et al. 2019). E3SM v1¹ features fully coupled ocean, sea-ice,
93 river, atmosphere and land components as well as a unique capability for multi-resolution model-
94 ing using unstructured grids in all of its components. The ocean and sea-ice components of E3SM
95 v1 are MPAS-Ocean and MPAS-Seaice respectively, which are built on the Model for Prediction
96 Across Scale (MPAS) modeling framework (Ringler et al. 2013; Petersen et al. 2019) and share
97 the same unstructured, horizontal mesh. The ocean model’s vertical grid is a structured, z-star co-
98 ordinate (Petersen et al. 2015; Reckinger et al. 2015) and uses 60 layers ranging from 10 m thick
99 at the surface to 250 m thick in the deep ocean. The ocean and sea-ice mesh used here contain
100 ~230,000 horizontal ocean cells with resolution varying from 30 to 60 km; enhanced resolution
101 in the equatorial and polar regions is used to better resolve processes of interest. Petersen et al.
102 (2019) provide a more detailed description of the E3SM v1 ocean and sea-ice components. The at-
103 mosphere component of E3SM v1 is the E3SM Atmospheric Model (EAM), which uses a spectral
104 element dynamical core at ~100 km horizontal resolution on a cubed-sphere geometry. EAM’s
105 vertical grid is a hybrid, sigma-pressure coordinate and uses 72 layers with a top of atmosphere
106 at approximately 60 km. Golaz et al. (2019), Xie et al. (2018), and Qian et al. (2018) provide a
107 detailed description of the E3SM v1 atmosphere component. Since there is currently no coupled

¹<https://github.com/E3SM-Project/E3SM/>

108 land ice component, E3SM v1 by default employs a “snowcapping” scheme, which routes water
109 stored on Antarctica (in the form of snow) back to the rest of the climate system. This conserves
110 mass globally and avoids having to account for a potentially large water sink in the model. When
111 snowcapping is active, any Antarctic precipitation that accumulates in excess of 1 m water equiv-
112 alent is immediately routed to the nearest coastal ocean grid cell and deposited at the surface with
113 a small amount of horizontal smoothing, thus functioning as a crude approximation to an ice sheet
114 in instantaneous equilibrium with climate forcing.

115 A new capability for Earth system models, now available in E3SM, is the extension of the ocean
116 domain to include ocean circulation in cavities under Antarctic ice shelves. In these cavities,
117 MPAS-Ocean solves the full prognostic equations, which include velocity, temperature, and salin-
118 ity. Based on these fields, we compute diagnostic melt fluxes from the base of the ice shelves
119 using coupled boundary conditions for heat and salt conservation, and a linearized equation of
120 state for the freezing point of seawater (Holland and Jenkins 1999; Hellmer and Olbers 1989).
121 These boundary conditions are used to simultaneously compute the potential temperature, salin-
122 ity, and melt rate at the ice shelf base using a velocity-dependent parameterization of the transfer
123 of heat and salt across the ocean-ice-shelf boundary layer (Dansereau et al. 2014) with constant,
124 non-dimensional heat- and salt-transfer coefficients (Jenkins et al. 2010). The boundary condi-
125 tions account only for the conversion of sensible heat from the ocean into latent heat of melting
126 ice, ignoring the sensible heat flux into the ice (which is typically $\lesssim 10\%$ of other terms; Holland
127 and Jenkins 1999). The thermal and haline driving terms are computed using “far-field” potential
128 temperature and salinity averaged over the top 10 m of the water column. The freshwater and heat
129 fluxes from ice-shelf melting are deposited into the ocean at depth using an exponentially decaying
130 distribution over the water column with a characteristic distance from the interface of 10 m. In the
131 simulations presented here, melt fluxes are computed directly in the ocean component once during

132 each ocean time step, rather than in the coupler. No overflow parameterizations, common in many
133 ESMs of similar resolution (Briegleb et al. 2010), are used to redistribute water masses between
134 ice-shelf cavities and the continental shelf or between the continental shelf and the deep ocean.
135 Given that E3SM does not yet have the ice sheet-ocean coupling needed to model the response
136 of the ice sheet to basal melting, we use a static geometry for the ice-shelf cavities and ground-
137 ing line. Thus, we are able to model the impact of ice-shelf melt fluxes on ocean circulation and
138 stratification, but not the feedback from ocean circulation and ice shelf basal melting on ice sheet
139 stability. Here, we assume that the term “ice-shelf melting” includes both melting and freezing
140 (i.e., negative melting) at the base of the ice shelf, but we label it “melting” because that term is
141 dominant.

142 To better understand and quantify the impact of these additional heat and freshwater fluxes in
143 an Earth system model, we have run a pair of fully-coupled, pre-industrial (Eyring et al. 2016)
144 simulations with E3SM: one with ice-shelf melt fluxes (hereafter, “ISM”)², and one without (here-
145 after, “Ctrl”)³. Previously published E3SM simulations (Golaz et al. 2019; Petersen et al. 2019) do
146 not include ice-shelf cavities, but the horizontal and vertical grids are otherwise identical to these.
147 Both ISM and Ctrl include the three-dimensional ocean domain below the ice shelves, but in Ctrl
148 the ice-shelf base is simply a depressed surface where no heat and freshwater exchange occur.
149 This experimental setup can be thought of as a sophisticated freshwater hosing experiment, where
150 the amount, timing, and location of the additional freshwater input to the system is model-state
151 dependent. As a result, the ISM simulation has an additional source term of freshwater (≈ 0.045
152 Sv) that is not in the Ctrl simulation (see Table 1 and Fig. 1). This difference in the freshwater
153 budget has the effect of an additional heat sink in the ISM simulation, since the freshwater from

²Full E3SM name: 20180612.B_case.T62_oEC60to30v3wLI.modified_runoff_mapping.edison, needed for referencing this run in the E3SM
archive

³Full E3SM name: 20180612.B_case.T62_oEC60to30v3wLI.modified_runoff_mapping.no_melt_fluxes.edison

154 ice-shelf melting is deposited in the ocean at the pressure- and salinity-dependent freezing point.
155 The simulations use “cold-start” initial conditions; the ocean is initialized with a month-long spin-
156 up (without ice-shelf melting) from rest for initial adjustment, and sea ice is initialized with a 1
157 meter-thick disk of ice extending to 65° in both hemispheres. Each simulation was run for 75
158 years, with model data from the last 30 years used for analysis.

159 *b. Atmosphere, ocean and sea-ice state estimates*

160 Before investigating the impacts of ice-shelf melting on WMT, we assess E3SM’s simulated
161 ocean temperature, salinity, and sea-ice properties over the Southern Ocean. To do this, we com-
162 pare E3SM results to several data sets including direct observations, model-based state estimates,
163 and interpolated climatologies of the ocean and sea-ice in this region. The Southern Ocean State
164 Estimate (SOSE, Mazloff et al. 2010) is a state-of-the-art data-assimilation product that incorpo-
165 rates millions of ocean and sea-ice observations while maintaining dynamically consistent ocean
166 state variables. Given the sparsity of observations in many regions around Antarctica, SOSE
167 offers a comprehensive, physically based estimate of ocean properties that would otherwise be
168 entirely uncharacterized. We also use the U.K. Met Office’s observational datasets (EN4; Good
169 et al. 2013), the World Ocean Atlas 2018 (WOA18; Locarnini et al. 2018), and the World Ocean
170 Circulation Experiment (WOCE)/Argo Global Hydrographic Climatology (WAGHC; Gouretski
171 2018), each of which provides a global data product of the subsurface ocean temperature and
172 salinity. For comparison of atmospheric winds over the Southern Ocean, we use zonal wind stress
173 from NCEP/NCAR Reanalysis I (Kalnay et al. 1996). For the sea-ice evaluation, we use several
174 satellite-derived observational data sets: sea-ice concentration from the SSM/I NASA Team (Cav-
175 alieri et al. 1996) and SSM/I Bootstrap (Comiso 1999) and sea-ice thickness from ICESat (Kurtz
176 and Markus 2012).

177 We note that these ocean and sea-ice data sets represent present-day conditions, whereas the
178 E3SM simulations are representative of model conditions for the the pre-industrial climate. While
179 there will be uncertainty when comparing pre-industrial simulation output with present-day ob-
180 servations, we find that the differences between pre-industrial and present-day control simulations
181 are much less than the differences between different model configurations under the same pre-
182 industrial forcing. Therefore, as in other studies (e.g., Menary et al. 2018), we feel justified in
183 using present-day observations as a metric by which to judge our pre-industrial simulation output.
184 Detailed information about each of these data sets, which have been time-averaged as indicated, is
185 provided in Table 2.

186 *c. Water mass transformation*

187 Water mass transformation analysis, first introduced by Walin (1982), quantifies the relationship
188 between the thermodynamic transformation of water mass properties within an ocean basin and
189 the net transport of those same properties into or out of the basin. This relationship has been used
190 to infer Southern Ocean overturning circulation based on observations of air-sea fluxes and to
191 characterize the thermodynamic processes that sustain the Southern Ocean overturning in models
192 (Abernathey et al. 2016). We have applied a new WMT analysis framework (based on Abernathey
193 et al. 2016) to aid in our investigation of Southern Ocean interactions between the atmosphere,
194 ocean, sea ice, and ice shelves, and to help identify biases in the E3SM’s representation of these
195 processes.

196 The Southern Ocean has steeply sloping isopycnals and weak diapycnal mixing, so water masses
197 are assumed to be primarily transformed by surface heat and freshwater fluxes (Toggweiler and
198 Samuels 1995; Speer et al. 2000; Wolfe and Cessi 2011; Nikurashin and Vallis 2012; Marshall and
199 Speer 2012; Talley 2013; Abernathey et al. 2016). As sea-ice growth, brine rejection and vertical

200 mixing have a tightly coupled relationship in the Southern Ocean, mixing-induced transformations
 201 are considered together with surface fluxes (Abernathey et al. 2016). Mixing-induced, interior dia-
 202 batic fluxes, however, were not written to output in our simulations and the interior diapycnal terms
 203 are relatively small in Circumpolar Deep Water (CDW) and Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW)
 204 density classes (Abernathey et al. 2016). Consequently, we only consider the transformation rate
 205 induced by surface fluxes.

206 The transformation across the density is derived from surface heat and freshwater buoyancy
 207 fluxes:

$$\Omega(\sigma_k, t) = -\frac{1}{\sigma_{k+1} - \sigma_k} \iint_A \left(\frac{\alpha Q_{net}}{\rho_0 C_p} \right) dA + \frac{1}{\sigma_{k+1} - \sigma_k} \iint_A \left(\frac{\beta SF_{net}}{\rho_0} \right) dA, \quad (1)$$

208 where variables in Equation 1 are defined in Table 3. In this study, the total WMT into the ocean
 209 consists of the transformation rate due to net surface heat flux (the first term of right-hand side in
 210 Equation 1) and the transformation rate due to net surface freshwater flux (the second term of right-
 211 hand side in Equation 1). The WMT is calculated numerically by discretizing potential density,
 212 σ_k , into 400 unevenly spaced bins. The bin spacing, $\sigma_{k+1} - \sigma_k$, varies from 0.025 kg m^{-3} at low
 213 densities to 0.0025 kg m^{-3} at high densities. This density spacing was chosen by Abernathey et al.
 214 (2016) who showed that it provides good resolution for high-density, polar water masses. In this
 215 study we analyze the WMT rate south of 60°S .

216 In E3SM, all the sources of net surface heat and freshwater fluxes, other than ice-shelf melt
 217 fluxes, are calculated in the coupler. Each term is stored separately in ocean history files. Here,
 218 “surface” implies processes at the atmosphere/ocean interface, but also at the sea ice/ocean and ice
 219 shelf/ocean interfaces. That is, the surface considered here is always the ocean surface regardless
 220 of what other model component that surface is in contact with.

221 To diagnose the role of different surface freshwater fluxes, we decompose surface net freshwater
 222 flux, F_{net} , into several sources:

$$F_{net} = F_{A \rightarrow O} + F_{I \rightarrow O} + F_{S \rightarrow O}, \quad (2)$$

223 where, $F_{A \rightarrow O}$ is the freshwater flux from the atmosphere into the ocean, $F_{I \rightarrow O}$ is that from sea-ice
 224 into the ocean and $F_{S \rightarrow O}$ is that from ice shelves into the ocean. $F_{I \rightarrow O}$ is further decomposed into
 225 two parts: the freshwater flux from sea-ice formation ($F_{\text{formation}}$) and that from sea-ice melting
 226 (F_{melting}):

$$F_{\text{formation}} = F_{I \rightarrow O} \text{ where } F_{I \rightarrow O} < 0, \quad (3)$$

$$F_{\text{melting}} = F_{I \rightarrow O} \text{ where } F_{I \rightarrow O} > 0. \quad (4)$$

227 The water mass formation (WMF) rate is the derivative of the transformation rate with respect to
 228 density,

$$M(\sigma) = -[\overline{\Omega(\sigma_{k+1})} - \overline{\Omega(\sigma_k)}], \quad (5)$$

229 where the over-bar represents an average in time.

230 The transformation and formation rate are computed with respect to surface-referenced potential
 231 density, but plotted against the neutral density, γ_n , using a regression relationship between potential
 232 density and neutral density (Jackett and McDougall 1997; Klocker et al. 2009). This is possible
 233 because surface-referenced potential density and neutral density have a robust linear relationship
 234 in the upper ocean (Abernathey et al. 2016). Table 4 shows how the WMT and formation rates
 235 should be physically interpreted with respect to their sign.

236 Following Abernathey et al. (2016), we classify Southern Ocean water masses into Thermocline
 237 Water (TW; $\gamma_n > 26.6 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$), Subantarctic Mode Water (SAMW; $26.6 < \gamma_n < 27.0 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$),
 238 Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW; $27.0 < \gamma_n < 27.5 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$), Upper Circumpolar Deep Water

239 (UCDW; $27.5 < \gamma_n < 28.0 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$), Lower Circumpolar Deep Water (LCDW; $28.0 < \gamma_n < 28.2$
240 kg m^{-3}), and Antarctic Bottom Water (AABW; $\gamma_n > 28.2 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$).

241 **3. Southern Ocean climate in E3SM**

242 Before looking in more detail at the impacts of ice-shelf melting on WMT in E3SM, we investi-
243 gate the fidelity of ocean temperature and salinity in simulation results from E3SM. In this section,
244 we use the Ctrl simulation to investigate the simulated Southern Ocean climate. Temperature and
245 salinity are the most important characteristics of seawater, in that they control ocean density and
246 further govern the vertical movement of ocean water. Fig. 2a and b show E3SM's annual mean
247 climatology for sea-surface temperature (SST) and salinity (SSS) over the Southern Ocean (south
248 of 50°S). The Southern Ocean is the coldest part of the global ocean, and is also relatively fresh,
249 with an area-averaged SST of 1.12°C and SSS of 33.4 PSU in E3SM (Fig. 2a and b). In Fig. 2c we
250 compare E3SM's SST and SSS with the four ocean products described in Section 2, in terms of
251 pattern correlation coefficients and normalized standard deviations over the Southern Ocean as a
252 Taylor diagram (Taylor 2001). The standard deviations in conventional Taylor diagrams show the
253 variability of time series data, but Fig. 2c shows the deviation of values at each grid point from the
254 area-averaged values for the annual mean field. The standard deviations of the four ocean prod-
255 ucts are then normalized by E3SM's standard deviation. The Taylor diagram shows that the spatial
256 variation of E3SM's SST is less than the four ocean products but E3SM's SSS have large spatial
257 variations. Nevertheless, both SST and SSS of E3SM have quite high (> 0.95) pattern correlation
258 coefficients with the four ocean products, demonstrating that E3SM has the ability to produce a
259 realistic Southern Ocean surface climate.

260 To investigate the characteristics of the potential temperature and salinity in the ocean interior,
261 Fig. 3 shows the full-depth, volumetric T-S diagram of the Southern Ocean for E3SM and the

262 four ocean data products. The volumetric T-S diagram, first introduced by Montgomery (1958),
263 presents a volumetric census for how much of a water mass has a given set of T-S properties
264 (Thomson and Emery 2014). The Southern Ocean near Antarctica has the densest, coldest water
265 in the global ocean. This dense water is referred to as AABW and is located at the bottom of
266 the T-S diagram ($\gamma_n > 28.2 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ in Fig. 3). In general, E3SM generates AABW at a similar
267 density to the four ocean data products. There are some discrepancies, however, in CDW ranges
268 ($\gamma_n < 28.2 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$), with E3SM having relatively colder temperatures between 1000m and 2000m
269 depths compared to the four ocean products. In the polar oceans, salinity is more important than
270 temperature in determining the density field, meaning the relatively colder temperatures in E3SM
271 do not affect the CDW density significantly.

272 It is also important to characterize how well E3SM represents that total water transported by
273 ocean currents. In Fig. 4 we show the horizontal and overturning volume transport in the Southern
274 Ocean for E3SM and SOSE. Positive values of the streamfunction in Fig. 4a, d show anticyclonic
275 subtropical gyres, while negative values represent cyclonic polar gyres. There is strong eastward
276 transport by the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC) between the subtropical and polar gyres, as
277 shown by the rapidly increasing contours from approximately 0 to 170 Sv in Fig. 4d. The results
278 from SOSE suggest that the Weddell gyre transport is almost double that of the Ross Sea gyre. In
279 general, E3SM simulates the horizontal volume transport well, as indicated by a reasonably high
280 pattern correlation coefficient of 0.98 between the horizontal circulation patterns from SOSE and
281 E3SM (Fig. 4a compared with d). The Meridional Overturning Circulation (MOC), calculated in
282 depth space, does not reflect cross-isopycnal flow (Speer et al. 2000). However it does make clear
283 the dominant Southern Ocean Ekman transport in E3SM and SOSE, which is due primarily to
284 the strong atmospheric westerly winds around 50°S (Fig. 4b and e). Closer to Antarctica, there
285 is relatively weak positive volume transport, resulting from a divergence of the Ekman transport,

286 which upwells water from ocean depths greater than 3000m (Fig. 4e). E3SM also simulates the
287 Southern Ocean overturning circulation reasonably well but displays relatively stronger equator-
288 ward Ekman transport (~ 41 Sv) compared to SOSE (~ 33 Sv) (Fig. 4b). This is due to relatively
289 stronger westerly winds in E3SM at around 50°S (Fig. 4c).

290 Because sea-ice formation and melting are dominant terms in causing CDW to upwell (Aber-
291 nathey et al. 2016) it is important to validate the properties of sea-ice in E3SM. Fig. 5 compares
292 E3SM's June-July-August (JJA) mean sea-ice concentration, October-November (ON) mean sea-
293 ice thickness, and annual mean freshwater flux from sea-ice into the Southern Ocean with SOSE
294 and satellite-based observations. Close to Antarctica, both E3SM and SOSE have Southern Hemi-
295 sphere winter sea-ice concentrations that are higher than observations (recall that E3SM is based
296 on pre-industrial conditions). E3SM has relatively thicker sea-ice compared to SOSE and ICESat
297 during October-November. This is a point that should be revisited in the future after acquiring
298 more updated sea-ice thickness observations in the Southern Ocean from ICESat-2 (Ice, Cloud,
299 and land Elevation Satellite 2). E3SM and SOSE are similar with respect to patterns of annual
300 mean freshwater flux from sea-ice to ocean (Fig. 5c), both having a similar magnitude of sea-
301 ice formation (corresponding to a negative freshwater flux) near Antarctica and sea-ice melting
302 (corresponding to a positive freshwater flux) offshore.

303 The above discussion argues that E3SM does a reasonable job of capturing the salient features of
304 Southern Ocean water masses, horizontal and overturning circulation, and sea-ice formation and
305 melting. We now move on to a comparative analysis of the Ctrl and ISM simulations.

306 **4. General impacts of ice shelf melting on hydrography and sea-ice over the Southern Ocean**

307 *a. Impacts on the Southern Ocean*

308 To investigate changes in hydrography over the Southern Ocean due to ice-shelf melting, we
309 show zonally averaged differences between the Ctrl and ISM simulations for ocean temperature,
310 salinity, and potential density, for specific basins of interest in the Indian, Pacific, and Atlantic
311 Oceans (Fig. 6). This comparison shows that the ISM simulation has a relatively fresher surface
312 near Antarctica (Fig. 6a, b, and c), with these salinity differences directly influencing the poten-
313 tial density distribution; the ISM simulation shows lower densities relative to the Ctrl simulation
314 (Fig. 6d, e, and f). The ISM simulation also shows depressed isopycnals near the Antarctic coast
315 in the Indian Ocean sector, which allows for the transport of relatively warm, deep water towards
316 the Antarctic coast rather than being ventilated at the ocean surface farther offshore (dashed line
317 in Fig. 6d, which continues to the coast rather than impinging on the surface). For the Pacific and
318 Atlantic Oceans, however, in the ISM simulation isopycnals impinge on topography at depth, trap-
319 ping relatively warm water there, inhibiting the access of warm CDW to the continental shelves
320 (relative to Ctrl). In general, surface freshening in the ISM simulation causes a more stratified ver-
321 tical ocean structure, especially near the Antarctic continental shelf (Fig. 7a vs. 7b). This prevents
322 convective activity between the surface and the ocean depths, resulting in relatively colder temper-
323 atures near the surface but warmer temperatures at depth. In turn, colder and fresher sea-surface
324 conditions in the ISM simulation result in more sea-ice formation near the Antarctic coast.

325 *b. Impacts on sea ice*

326 To investigate the impacts on sea ice over the Southern Ocean, we examine the differences in
327 mean annual sea-ice concentration, thickness, and sea-ice to ocean freshwater flux between the

328 Ctrl and ISM simulations (Fig. 8). Sea ice concentration in the ISM simulation has increased by
329 an area average of 5% and the sea-ice thickness has increased by about 15 cm over the Southern
330 Ocean (Fig. 8a, b), compared to the Ctrl simulation. Further, we find that more freezing occurs in
331 the ISM than the Ctrl simulation (Fig. 8c) and that spatial pattern of these differences is similar to
332 those for sea-ice concentration (Fig. 8a). The ISM simulation shows a similar sea-ice expansion
333 as discussed by Bintanja et al. (2013), who argued that the overall increase in observed sea-ice
334 concentration is dominated by increased ice-shelf melting. As suggested by Bintanja et al. (2013),
335 ice-shelf melting freshens the surface, which reduces convective activity between the (less dense)
336 fresh surface and the (more dense) warmer subsurface layers. This cools the upper ocean, which,
337 along with fresher surface waters, encourages more sea-ice formation (here, at an average rate of
338 -0.05 m/yr; Fig. 8c). Whereas Bintanja et al. (2013) put freshwater fluxes from ice-shelf melting
339 at the ocean surface, our ISM simulation places that freshwater at the depth of the ice-shelf base,
340 inducing overturning that may either enhance or suppress local sea-ice formation, depending on
341 deeper ocean conditions (Donat-Magnin et al. 2017; Jourdain et al. 2017; Mathiot et al. 2017).

342 **5. Water mass transformation and formation from ice-shelf melting**

343 *a. Water mass transformation*

344 We show the annual mean WMT rate from the Ctrl and ISM simulations in Fig. 9. Broadly
345 speaking, there are no significant differences in WMT rates due to the total surface fluxes, which
346 are a summation of surface heat and freshwater fluxes (black lines in Fig. 9a). We do, however,
347 find important differences in the individual components; if we further separate the WMT rate into
348 that caused by distinct sources of freshwater flux (Fig. 9b), we see compensating differences in
349 transformation rate between the Ctrl and ISM simulations for each source of freshwater flux. First,

350 freshwater flux from ice-shelf melting induces a negative transformation rate (buoyancy gain) by
351 as much as -1.74 Sv (peaking at a neutral density of 27.4 kg m^{-3}) compared to the Ctrl simulation.
352 Second, ice-shelf melting also significantly affects sea ice indirectly. The transformation rate due
353 to sea-ice formation and melting increases by as much as 1.79 Sv, at the same high density levels
354 ice-shelf melting affects, but decreases by -0.84 Sv at lower densities (with the largest decrease at
355 26.4 kg m^{-3}). Third, we find no notable changes in the transformation rate by freshwater fluxes
356 from the atmosphere and land (E-P-R term) between the two simulations.

357 In Fig. 10, we plot the climatological annual cycle of WMT rate caused by freshwater fluxes
358 from sea-ice formation and melting and from ice-shelf melting. Consistent with Fig. 9, ice-shelf
359 melting always produces a negative transformation rate (Fig. 10b), regardless of the season, at
360 around a neutral density level of 27.4 kg m^{-3} . In contrast, the transformation caused by sea-ice
361 formation and melting has large seasonal variability (Fig. 10a), with a positive transformation
362 rate (buoyancy loss) during the winter and a negative transformation rate (buoyancy gain) during
363 the summer. These differences in transformation rate between the two simulations (Fig. 10c)
364 show that the ISM simulation has an overall stronger seasonal sea ice cycle. During winter, the
365 ISM simulation has a more positive transformation rate due to sea-ice formation, peaking at a
366 neutral density of 27.4 kg m^{-3} where ice-shelf melting is also dominant. During summer, the ISM
367 simulation has a more negative transformation rate through sea-ice melting at lower density levels,
368 which compensates for the more positive transformation rate in winter.

369 *b. Water mass formation*

370 Finally, we investigate how ice-shelf melting and sea-ice formation and melting impact water
371 mass formation and destruction by decomposing the water mass formation rate into contributions
372 from different surface flux processes (Fig. 11). The water mass formation rate is the difference

373 of the WMT rate with respect to density and represents volume convergence (for positive values,
374 corresponding to downwelling) or divergence (for negative values, corresponding to upwelling)
375 within a particular density range (Abernathy et al. 2016). The freshwater flux from ice-shelf melt-
376 ing can thus indirectly impact the water mass formation rate through sea-ice formation and melting
377 (Fig. 11a). For both the Ctrl and ISM simulation, the combined effects of sea-ice formation and
378 melting destroy a considerable amount of water mass (corresponding to a negative formation rate)
379 in the density range from 26.4 kg m^{-3} to 27.4 kg m^{-3} (some parts of TW, SAMW, and AAIW).
380 Yet there is additional water mass destruction in this same density range by as much as 2.57 Sv
381 per year for the ISM simulation (Table 5). The freshwater flux from ice-shelf melting directly
382 induces upwelling (corresponding to a negative formation rate) at relatively high-density levels
383 (UCDW and LCDW) and this upwelled water is directly converted to lower densities (Fig. 11b).
384 The total amount of upwelling due to ice-shelf melting is approximately 1.77 Sv per year (Table 5).
385 Fig. 11c-f shows the WMF rate for the Southern Ocean divided into the Indian Ocean, Ross Sea,
386 Amundsen Sea And Weddell Sea sectors. It is evident that the Indian Sea sector dominates the
387 WMF rate, and that upwelled water here is converted to relatively low densities. This is probably
388 due to relatively warm water coming up onto the continental shelf in the Indian Ocean sector in
389 the ISM simulation (Fig. 6g), and thus melt rates are probably too high compared to Rignot et al.
390 (2013) (e.g., note large melt biases in Dronning Maud Land region and for the Amery Ice Shelf in
391 Fig. 1). The Indian Ocean sector (the Dronning Maud Land region of Antarctica) has a particularly
392 narrow continental shelf, and the model resolution is likely insufficient to separate warmer water
393 in the deeper Weddell Sea from colder water trapped on the continental shelf.

394 **6. Summary and conclusions**

395 By comparing otherwise identical Earth system model simulations with and without ice-shelf
396 melt fluxes we have used E3SM to characterize and quantify the impacts of ice-shelf melting and
397 freezing processes on WMT and WMF. We find no significant differences in net Southern Ocean
398 WMT due to the differences in total surface fluxes between the two simulations. Yet when we
399 separate the WMT rate into its constituent processes we find important differences in both WMT
400 and WMF rate between the simulations. Meltwater from ice shelves makes AAIW and UCDW
401 water masses in the Southern Ocean lighter (corresponding to a buoyancy gain) at relatively high
402 density values. Meanwhile, the freshwater flux from sea-ice formation makes these water masses
403 denser (corresponding to a buoyancy loss) at these same high density values. Effectively, ice-shelf
404 meltwater is partially counteracting the densification of seawater from brine rejection at these
405 densities, with even more of a cancellation likely under future climate scenarios in which ice-
406 shelf melting is likely to increase. Ice-shelf melting produces upwelling of UCDW water masses
407 at relatively high density values where ice-shelf melting is dominant and this upwelled water is
408 directly converted to lower density values. Freshwater fluxes produced by ice-shelf melting have
409 a further, indirect impact on the Southern Ocean overturning circulation through the action of
410 increased sea-ice formation and melting, which also cause considerable upwelling and effectively
411 further amplifies the overturning that occurs from the buoyancy of ice-shelf meltwater directly.
412 Importantly, we find that this indirect impact is larger than the direct impact.

413 We have found that surface freshening by ice-shelf melting increases density stratification near
414 the Antarctic coast and hence reduces vertical heat transport from the deeper ocean, trapping
415 warmer water at depth. In some regions, this trapped heat might be expected to reach ice-shelf
416 cavities through changes in ocean currents and/or density structure in future climate scenarios.

417 Indeed, in some regions of Antarctica, that feedbacks between ice-shelf melting and trapping
418 of warmer waters has already been observed (Silvano et al. 2018). This more stratified ocean
419 makes the sea surface colder, which along with the additional freshwater, results in significant
420 Antarctic sea-ice expansion in simulations that include ice shelf melt fluxes. Our findings of
421 sea-ice expansion by ice-shelf melting suggest that increased ice-shelf melting over the past few
422 decades (e.g., Shepherd et al. 2004; Pritchard et al. 2012; Khazendar et al. 2016) could be a cause
423 for the observed sea-ice expansion over that same time. These findings are also consistent with
424 previous studies investigating the relationship between ice-shelf melting and Antarctic sea-ice
425 expansion (Bintanja et al. 2013; Pauling et al. 2016; Bintanja et al. 2015; Bronselaer et al. 2018).

426 Abernathey et al. (2016) assessed the relative contributions of sea-ice freezing and melting,
427 together with other modes of air-sea interaction, to Southern Ocean overturning and revealed the
428 central role of sea-ice formation and melting in transforming upwelled Circumpolar Deep Water.
429 Although we found no significant changes to those conclusions in this study, our results do show
430 that the addition of ice-shelf melting to Earth system models increases the importance of sea-ice in
431 Southern Ocean overturning. In other words, the increase in Antarctic ice-shelf melting over the
432 historical time period (Shepherd et al. 2004; Pritchard et al. 2012; Khazendar et al. 2016; Holland
433 et al. 2019) has increased the role of sea-ice in Southern Ocean overturning.

434 Even though we have not seen significant differences in Southern Ocean WMT related to ice-
435 shelf melting in this study, Silvano et al. (2018) suggested that increased glacial melt water will
436 reduce AABW formation by offsetting increased salt flux during sea-ice formation in coastal
437 polynyas. These effects would then prevent full-depth convection and the formation of dense
438 shelf water. In this study we have used a relatively low resolution version of E3SM, which does
439 not have a good representation of Antarctic coastal polynyas. This may explain why we do not find

440 changes in dense water formation related to ice-shelf melting. Future E3SM studies will investi-
441 gate the impacts of ice-shelf melting and the inclusion of ice-shelf cavities at higher resolution.

442 Ice-shelf melting is not uniform along the Antarctic coast (Rignot et al. 2013; Depoorter et al.
443 2013), suggesting the possibility for strong regional contrasts in how it effects sea ice. Thus, care
444 must be taken in how Antarctic ice-shelf melt is distributed along the coast in global, coupled
445 climate simulations. Here, prognostic basal melt fluxes from individually modeled ice shelves
446 influence and are, in turn, affected by regional differences in sea-ice expansion and WMT. In that
447 sense, the E3SM model used here is a useful tool for investigating potential feedbacks between
448 Antarctic ice-shelves and ocean and sea-ice properties on the way to developing an Earth system
449 model coupled to an active ice-sheet component.

450 While in this study we only consider the impacts of ice-shelf melting on the Southern Ocean,
451 iceberg melting represents approximately half of the mass flux from the Antarctic ice sheet to the
452 ocean (Rignot et al. 2013; Depoorter et al. 2013). Calved icebergs transport freshwater flux away
453 from the Antarctic coast and exchange heat with the ocean, thereby affecting ocean stratification
454 and circulation, with subsequent indirect thermodynamic effects on the sea-ice system (Hunke and
455 Comeau 2011; Stern et al. 2016; Merino et al. 2016). Future work to address these effects should
456 include a comprehensive analysis considering the impacts of both melting from ice shelves and
457 calved icebergs.

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	Ctrl	ISM
Runoff	0.087 (0.042) Sv	0.080 (0.041) Sv
Ice-shelf melting	0 Sv	0.045 (0.003) Sv
Total	0.087 (0.042) Sv	0.125 (0.041) Sv

TABLE 2. Atmosphere, ocean and sea-ice estimation datasets used in this study.

Data sets	Variables	Periods	Reference
NCEP/NCAR Reanalysis I	Zonal wind stress	2005-2010	(Kalnay et al. 1996)
SOSE	Temperature, Salinity,	2005-2010	(Mazloff et al. 2010)
	Sea-ice concentration,	2005-2010	
	Sea-ice thickness,	2005-2010	
	Zonal and meridional components of velocity,	2005-2010	
	Sea-ice to ocean freshwater flux	2005-2010	
EN4	Temperature, Salinity	1995-2018	(Good et al. 2013)
WOA18	Temperature, Salinity	1995-2018	(Locarnini et al. 2018)
WAGHC	Temperature, Salinity	1985-2016	(Gouretski 2018)
SSM/I NASATeam	Sea-ice concentration	1979-2009	(Cavalieri et al. 1996)
SSM/I Bootstrap	Sea-ice concentration	1979-2009	(Comiso 1999)
ICESat	Sea-ice thickness	2003-2008	(Kurtz and Markus 2012)

TABLE 3. Definition of parameter in Equation 1 and 5

Parameter	Description	Units
Ω	WMT rate	Sv
M	WMF rate	Sv
σ_k	Surface-referenced potential density	kg m^{-3}
t	Time	s
α	Thermal expansion	$\text{kg m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$
Q_{net}	Downward surface heat flux	W m^{-2}
C_p	Specific heat of seawater (3,994)	$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
β	Haline coefficient of contraction	$\text{kg m}^{-3} \text{PSU}^{-1}$
F_{net}	Downward surface freshwater flux	$\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
S	Sea surface salinity	PSU
ρ_0	Constant reference density of seawater (1,035)	kg m^{-3}
A	Horizontal ocean surface area of interest	m^2

TABLE 4. Interpretation of WMT and formation rate.

	Positive	Negative
Transformation rates	Denser	Lighter
	Lose buoyancy	Gain buoyancy
Formation rates	Water convergence	Water divergence
	Downwelling motion	Upwelling motion

669 TABLE 5. Thirty-year annual mean of upwelled water from ocean depths caused by either freshwater flux from
 670 ice-shelf melting or from sea-ice formation and melting. Rows show results from the ISM and Ctrl simulations,
 671 and their differences. Values in parenthesis represent the standard deviation over 30 years of the annual mean
 672 (indicating the level of interannual variability) of upwelled water in each simulation.

	Ice-shelf melting	Sea-ice formation and melting
ISM	-1.77 (0.12) Sv	-19.04 (1.75) Sv
Ctrl	N/A	-16.47 (1.56) Sv
ISM - Ctrl	-1.77 Sv	-2.57 Sv

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